

BASICS OF PERFORMING SKILLS IN PERCUSSION INSTRUMENTS

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Abstract: The rich musical heritage of Uzbekistan cannot be imagined without percussion instruments. These instruments are important in the preservation and development of national musical traditions. In this article, we tried to consider the use and importance of percussion instruments in the musical culture of Uzbekistan, how widespread they are and what role they play in musical works.

Key words: Uzbek folk instruments, percussion instruments, melodic, harmonic, rhythmic, Circle, harmony, repertoire.

Introduction:

According to sources, the history of national musical instruments goes back to very distant times. That is, as early as the 13th thousand years before our era, percussion instruments, and then loud sounds, began to appear. The great scientists explain why the words with percussion were discovered for the first time, as the oldest work songs were created in direct connection with the rhythmic structure of work. Later, folk craftsmen made instruments such as trumpets, flutes, whistles, rattles, and chiltar (harp) from reeds or bamboo stalks. After a certain period, stringed mizrab and stringed bowed musical instruments were created.

During the long historical development, different types of percussion instruments were formed in the musical practice of different peoples in terms of their structure, sound generation, performance and expressiveness. According to the well-known scientist T. Vizgo, the mudovara (plate) is also among the military instruments. Similar mudovara (sanj) were known three thousand years before AD, but they have reached our time in their own form like a circle instrument. Percussion instruments - doyra, debu, tambourine, daz, dov, sanj, golachalar were created two thousand years before Melod (Nisadian period) and have been improved with various forms, structures and percussions and have reached us. The musicologist T. Vizgo thinks about the history of the circle and the methods of playing the sange instrument, and emphasizes that the sange instrument is played with a ribbon through the middle, and it is played in the same way in the present time.

To achieve pop music and its performance, the use of drum and drum set performance techniques, which are the basis of this direction, cannot be achieved. In pop music, the task of the Drummer is to create the main musical rhythm of the group. The rhythm is based on the alternation of the low sound of the bass drum and the high, sharp sound of the snare drum. In addition to this primary function, the drummer emphasizes and embellishes key accents and changes in the melody. The main method of drumming is percussion. There are many different types of tattooing. Their differences can be seen even in their names: they are single upstroke, single downstroke, double wrist stroke, double toe stroke, single leg stroke, double

leg stroke, cross stick stroke, triple stroke. In addition to the striking method, the types of holding positions of wooden sticks are also of great importance. In the traditional grip, the right hand usually uses a parallel grip (pictured below), while the left hand holds the baton palm up between the index and ring fingers. The traditional stick grip is more popular in jazz than any other style, and is also used by rock drummers.

Even when playing on a stand, many drummers bend their drums slightly when using the traditional stick grip. It is done by grasping the lower part of the drumstick with the index and middle fingers of the hand and fixing it with the thumb from above. Holding the sticks in this way allows the stick to move freely and bounce (return) when the beat is played.

While studying the main performance methods of playing percussion instruments, we emphasize their variety and breadth of timbre characteristics, the complexity of performance, and emphasize that performance skills should be properly organized at the initial stages of training.

The "correct" position (position or post) of the drummer. This position (postanovka) includes such a position of the body and hands, in which the muscles of the drummer take the least load when performing the necessary movements during the performance. To get the correct position of the body, the following tasks are assigned to the drummer:

1. The height of the seat should be adjusted to such a height that the performer's pelvis should be approximately 10-15 cm above the knee.
2. The performer should straighten the lower back - a bent back greatly reduces the endurance of the drummer.
3. In order to get the right position of the hands, you need to grab the sticks in any position and lower your hands, relax all the joints: shoulders, elbows, hands; bend your elbows forward about 90 degrees; point the ends of the sticks towards the center of the drum.

The main techniques of drumming are the "Single beat" technique. This is an action that consists of a real kick with a wide arm. It doesn't matter which grip position you use to perform this technique, the execution technique remains the same in any grip position. 1. It is necessary to choose the right position of the drummer. 2. When lifting the arms: move the elbow forward so that it is at the level of the shoulder or slightly lower (it is important to perform the movement in such a way that the elbow goes forward or back), the arm is relaxed, the shoulder is kept parallel or almost in the same position.

3. Kick: relax your shoulders, as a result of which the elbow returns to its original position. In this case, it is necessary to act with the wrist (cyst). The main point is to focus on the maximum relaxation of the wrist joint, as a result of which a strong impact is achieved.

4. Accepting the wand's return. As soon as the hand returns to its original position, the stick hits the surface of the drum, it bounces off the surface. To do this, do not tighten the hand and fingers when touching the rod to the plastic coating, but relax them, which will dampen the force of the rod return. It is worth mentioning the punching technique, which has a more complex, circular movement of the elbow during movement. This coin is widely used now. Unfortunately, in the process of teaching children, this method is not used in practice, it is encouraged to teach the child more theoretical and technical elements, which can extinguish the child's interest in music.

Working with a drum brush. Brushes are a very versatile dynamic and tonal device. Just as single and double strokes are performed on wooden sticks, we can perform such strokes on brushes. But the double stroke (since there is no jumping movement after the stroke, no

jumping back) is performed not with fingers, but with a brush. Brushes are widely used in jazz music and very slow pieces of music called ballads. Their main feature is that you can create a "whisper" sound and fill the gaps between beats with this sound.

Art educational institutions (music schools, secondary and higher educational institutions, etc.) are mainly professional education, training professional performers and specialists. Regardless of the chosen form of training (amateur or professional), the methods (techniques) of sound generation are the same in all percussion instruments.

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